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WEBINAR

Access policies and usage regulations: licenses

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Topics

Who benefits?

Challenges

What is a license?

Licensing agreement

Creative Commons

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Who benefits from sharing research data?

The public

The research sponsor/funder

The research community

The researcher

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Challenges of preserving and sharing research data

Infrastructure

Lack of incentives

IPR/Ownership

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What is a license?

A legal document that lets the copyright holder allow other people to use the copyrighted work and do things that would otherwise be an infringement of copyright.

Licensing can be done by the rights holder and can specify various conditions for the use of the copyrighted work. Usually, the rights holder retains all the rights, unless the license explicitly states otherwise.

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CESSDA Archives licenses

License

Licensing agreement

End user licence

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A licensing agreement should cover:

Ownership/IPR

Legal issues

The rights and responsibilities of
the archive and the depositor

Access conditions

Source: <http://training.dasish.eu/training/1/3/8.html#refcessda3>

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The End User License should cover:

Access conditions

Acknowledgements

Special conditions

Source: <http://training.dasish.eu/training/1/3/8.html#refcessda3>

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Creative Commons

- nonprofit organization
- enables sharing through free legal tools
- easy-to-use copyright licenses
- “some rights reserved”

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Creative Commons License Generator

License Features

Your choices on this panel will update the other panels on this page.

Allow adaptations of your work to be shared?

Yes No

Yes, as long as others share alike

Allow commercial uses of your work?

Yes No

Selected License

Attribution 4.0 International

This is a Free Culture License!

Help others attribute you!

This part is optional, but filling it out will add machine-readable metadata to the suggested HTML!

Title of work

Attribute work to name

Attribute work to URL

Source work URL

More permissions URL

Format of work

License mark

Have a web page?

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Copy this code to let your visitors know!

```
<a rel="license" href="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"></a><br />This work is licensed under a <a rel="license"
```

Normal Icon Compact Icon

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Q&A

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thanks!

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